

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

CASE REPORT ON THROMBOLYTIC THERAPY ASSOCIATED PONTINE HAEMORRHAGE AND ITS RISK FACTORS.

Dr. Soniya Davis^{1*}, Dr. Anju Paul¹, Dr Chinnu Reeba George¹, Dr. Priya Thomas¹, Dr. Arun Kumar², Dr. Jessy Thomas³

¹Department of Clinical Pharmacy, Lisie Hospital.

²Department of Neurology, Lisie Hospital.

³Department of Paediatric, Lisie Hospital

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 17/02/2018

Available online

28/02/2018

Keywords

Recombinant Tissue Plasminogen Activator (rtPA)
Acute Ischemic Stroke.

ABSTRACT

Thrombolytic therapy is of proven and substantial benefit for patients with Acute Ischemic Stroke. But the intracranial haemorrhage associated with thrombolysis said to be the most dreaded complication. This is a case report of thrombolysis induced intracranial haemorrhage that lead to the death of a 65year old male patient with the history of Acute Ischemic Stroke. Factors that influence risk of thrombolytic therapy associated intracranial haemorrhage are low body weight, age greater than 65years, history of Hypertension, Diabetes Mellitus, use of anticoagulant drugs before admission, heparin therapy during admission, smoking and alcoholism. Therefore patients who are at increased risk should be recognised earlier. One suggestion would be to lower the dose of thrombolytic agents, recombinant tissue Plasminogen Activator (rtPA) in patients who are at greatest risk. If these risks can be minimised through better recognition of risk factors and appropriate dosing, then the thrombolytic therapy can be effectively used.

Corresponding author

Dr. Soniya Davis

Department of Clinical Pharmacy,
Lisie Hospital.

Please cite this article in press as **Dr. Soniya Davis et al. Case Report on Thrombolytic Therapy Associated Pontine Haemorrhage And its Risk Factors. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2018;8(02).**

Copy right © 2018 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Acute Ischemic Stroke causes significant morbidity and is one of the leading cause of death worldwide.^[1] Acute management of stroke in hospitals can be done by confirmatory CT scan diagnosis and thrombolysis(NICE 2011). Intravenous thrombolysis within 3 hours of onset of symptoms, use of aspirin within 48 hours and decompressive surgery for malignant middle cerebral artery infarction has become the impetus for improved acute thrombotic stroke treatment across the world (Pandian 2008).^[2] Intravenous administration of Alteplase is the US FDA approved mainstay medical therapy for Acute Ischemic Stroke^[3]. Early mobilization is considered as a priority in order to prevent disabilities and promote function (NICE 2011). Stroke patients are managed in stroke units that have been shown to be effective in terms of recovery and return to active life (Pandian 2008). Thrombolysed patients are expected to have early neurological recovery, reduced hospital stay and better functional outcomes at 3 months post stroke (Blinzer 2011). Post-acute management of stroke patients depends on the severity and site of lesion^[2]. Although intravenous thrombolysis remains the mainstay treatment for acute ischemic stroke, thrombolysis-related complications can even lead to intracranial haemorrhage^[4]

Pontine haemorrhage represents approximately 5% of ICH cases^[5]. Intracranial haemorrhage is the most dreaded complication of thrombolytic therapy in which recombinant tissue Plasminogen Activator (rtPA) was administered in patients with acute ischemic stroke. According to American Stroke Association, patient with uncontrolled HTN, coagulopathy, and a history of ICH should be excluded from the administration of rtPA. They found the prevalence of ICH is about 3.7% to 6.5% in patient receiving thrombolytic therapy^[6]. Pontine haemorrhage is characterised by sudden onset of coma, constricted pupils, quadriplegia, and early respiratory arrest. Death usually occurs within minutes to hours and the treatment is conservative. The condition most likely lead to primary pontine haemorrhage was hypertension, that has affected about two third of patients.^[7] Intracranial haemorrhage should be suspected if there is any acute neurological deterioration, new headache, nausea or vomiting, acute increase in blood pressure.^[8]

ALTEPLASE ADMINISTRATION FOR ACUTE ISCHAEMIC STROKE

Alteplase is a thrombolytic agent which can be used to treat acute ischemic stroke. It should be administered as soon as possible but within 3 hours after onset of symptoms. The recommended dose is 0.9 mg/kg (not to exceed 90 mg total dose), with 10% of the total dose administered as an initial intravenous bolus over 1 minute and the remainder infused over 60 minutes. During and following Alteplase administration for the treatment of acute ischemic stroke, frequently monitor and control blood pressure.

In patients without recent use of oral anticoagulants or heparin, Alteplase treatment can be initiated prior to the availability of coagulation study results. Discontinue Alteplase if the pre-treatment International Normalized Ratio (INR) is greater than 1.7 or the activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) is elevated.

In clinical studies patients with Acute ischemic stroke (Studies 1 and 2) the incidence of intracranial haemorrhage, was higher in Alteplase-treated patients than in placebo patients⁷. A dose finding study of Alteplase suggested that dose greater than 0.9 mg/kg may be associated with an increased incidence of intracranial haemorrhage.

CASE REPORT

A 65 year old male patient came to Emergency department with complaints of weakness of left upper and lower limbs, facial deviation and slurring of speech. The patient was not having any past medical history of DM, HTN and DLP. Vital signs were checked and BP was elevated to 200/100mmHg. He was administered with inj.Labetalol 20mg, and then Bp was found to be 185/110mmHg. Patient was diagnosed as Acute Ischemic Stroke with confirmation of CT scan. Patient lab investigations showed INR and PT in normal range, but aPTT was 1.03 and CPK 92. Patient shifted to Neuro medical ICU and thrombolysed with Inj. Actiplase 5 units stat and 40 units over 1hr within 2hrs of admission. At that time his BP was 200/100mmHg, Tab. Arkamin was administered as the patient BP still remains same even after 1hr of thrombolysis. The patient become stable and the power of left lower and upper limbs were improved. After 3 hrs, GRBS was 169mg/dl and patient complaints about right sided weakness. Repeated CT showed interventricular bleeding/pontine haemorrhage. Bp fall present and poor prognosis of patient condition was found. His condition gradually worsened and he expired.

DISCUSSION

Among the haemorrhagic complications caused by the thrombolytic agents, intracranial haemorrhage is considered as the major adverse effect. Some reports demonstrate that the local factors like vascular integrity and local action of plasmin are responsible for these events. They also proposed that there will be failure to achieve haemostasis when a vascular lesion occurs during thrombolysis due to lysis of a pre-existing blood clot.^[9]

According to the case control study conducted by Peter P De Jaegere et al they found intracranial haemorrhage induced by thrombolytics starts within 24 hour after initiation of treatment^[9]. But the incidence of cerebral infarction was found to start after 48 hour of the thrombolytic therapy. Reported incidence rates for intracranial haemorrhage in medium and large trials vary 0% to 1.4%^[10]. Bleeding is considered as the major problem associated with thrombolytic therapy. A current study proposed that 11% of patients who receive thrombolytic agents have reasonable bleeding^[11]. Therefore the patients who are at increased risk for bleeding and other haemorrhagic complications should be recognised.

Factors that influence the risk of thrombolytic therapy induced haemorrhagic complications are low body weight, age >65 yrs, history of hypertension, diabetes mellitus, anticoagulant drugs before admission, heparin therapy during admission, hypertension at admission, smoking and alcoholism.

According to the trial conducted by Braunwald E et al they found that overdosing of alteplase in patients with low body weight is a higher risk for intracranial haemorrhage. Hence dose was changed from 150 to 100mg/6h during the thrombolytic therapy.^[12]

Pontine haemorrhage frequently causes severe disturbances of consciousness, oculomotor disturbances, tetra paresis, and respiratory failure. In a recent study the prognosis was found to be highly fatal, with the overall mortality rate being 40–50%.^[13]

The presence of uncontrolled hypertension during thrombolytic therapy increases the risk for intracranial haemorrhage. Many studies have confirmed that the rate of intracranial haemorrhage with r-tpa administration and uncontrolled hypertension is 26% compared to 12% in those without uncontrolled hypertension^[14]. Study demonstrates that r-tpa trial with a blood pressure of less than 185/110 mmHg before therapy and less than 180/105 mmHg after the therapy can reduce the risk factors.

The study conducted by NINDS states that the rate of intracranial haemorrhage in patients with hyperglycaemia treated with r-tpa was 25%. Therefore it is said that hyperglycaemia or diabetes to be a risk for intracranial haemorrhage^[15].

CONCLUSION

Though thrombolytic therapy has potential side effects, if these risks can be minimised through better recognition of risk factors and appropriate dosing, then thrombolytic therapy can be effectively used. Patients using oral anticoagulants before admission and those with a low body weight and age >65 years seems to be at higher risk. For the patients who are at increased risk for the therapy a risk–benefit analysis would be helpful before the therapy and they should be monitored closely.

REFERENCE

1. Thompson Robinson, Zahid Zaheer, and Amit K. Mistri. Thrombolysis in Acute Ischemic Stroke: An Update. *Ther Adv Chronic Dis.* 2011 Mar; 2(2): 119–131.
2. Daniel J. Miller, Jennifer R. Simpson, and Brian Silver. Safety of Thrombolysis in Acute Ischemic Stroke: A Review of Complications, Risk Factors, and Newer Technologies. *The Neurohospitalist* 2011; 1(3) 138-147
3. Sameer Bansal, Kiranpal S. Sangha, and Pooja Khatri. Drug Treatment of Acute Ischemic Stroke. *Am J Cardiovasc Drugs.* 2013 Feb; 13(1): 10.1007/s40256-013-00076.
4. Shadi Yaghi, Andrew Eisenberger, Joshua Z. Willey. Symptomatic Intracerebral Hemorrhage in Acute Ischemic Stroke After Thrombolysis With Intravenous Recombinant Tissue Plasminogen Activator: A Review of Natural History and Treatment. *JAMA Neurol.* 2014; 71(9): 1181-1185.
5. Vlak MH, Algra A, Brandenburg T, Rinkel GJ. Prevalence of unruptured intracranial aneurysms, with emphasis on sex, age, co morbidity, country and time period: A systematic review and meta analysis. *Lancet Neurol.* 2011; 10 (7): 626-36.
6. Ehud Lavi, Steve Rothman, Avinoam Reches. Primary Pontine Hemorrhage With Complete Recovery. *Arch Neurol.* 1981; 38(5): 320.
7. Department of Health, Western Australia. Protocol for Administering Alteplase in Acute Ischaemic Stroke Guidelines. Perth: Health Networks Branch, Department of Health, Western Australia; 2011.
8. Tracy Rp, Bovill EG. Fibrinolytic parameters and hemostatic monitoring: identifying and predicting patient at risk for major hemorrhagic events. *Am J Cardiol* 1992; 69: 52 A-9A.
9. De Jargere pp, Arnold AA, Balk AH et al. Intracranial hemorrhage in association with thrombolytic therapy: incidence and clinical predictive factors. *J Am Coll Cardiol* 1992; 19: 289-94.
10. Gore JM, Sloan Ms, Price ThR, et al. Intracerebral haemorrhage, cerebral infarction, and sudden hematoma after acute myocardial infarction and thrombolytic therapy in the thrombolysis in Myocardial infarction study. *Thrombolysis in Myocardial infarction, phase II, pilot and clinical trial. Circulation* 1991; 83: 448-59.
11. Md. Ramjan Ali, Mohammad Salim Hossain, Md. Ariful Islam, Md. Saiful Islam Arman, Golam Sarwar Raju, Prianka Dasgupta, and Tasnim Fariha Noshin. 'Aspect of Thrombolytic Therapy: A Review' *The Scientific World Journal* Volume 2014 (2014), Article ID 586510, 8 pages
12. Braunwald E, Knatterud GL, Passamani E, Robertson TL, Solomon R. Update from the thrombolysis in myocardial infarction trial. *J Am Coll Cardiol* 1987; 10: 970.

13. Tiemo Wessels, Walter Möller-Hartmann, Johannes Noth and Christof Klötzsch. CT Findings and Clinical Features as Markers for Patient Outcome in Primary Pontine Haemorrhage .American Journal of Neuroradiology February 2004, 25 (2) 257-260;
14. Sherif Hafez , Maha Coucha, Askiel Bruno, Susan C. Fagan, and Adviye Ergul 'Hyperglycemia, Acute Ischemic Stroke and Thrombolytic Therapy' Transl Stroke Res. 2014 Aug; 5(4): 442–453. .
15. Saver JL. Haemorrhage after thrombolytic therapy for stroke: the clinically relevant number needed to harm. Stroke. 2007;38(8):2279-2283.

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

- Convenient online manuscript submission
- Access Online first
- Double blind peer review policy
- International recognition
- No space constraints or color figure charges
- Immediate publication on acceptance
- Inclusion in **ScopeMed** and other full-text repositories
- Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

